

Direct Calculation of Radial Band Structures in Circular Gratings via a Generalized Bloch Condition: Supplement

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This supplement formulates the generalized Bloch condition for circular gratings, providing a mathematical framework for analyzing wave propagation in radially periodic media.

1. The Radial Helmholtz Equation

To establish a rigorous mathematical framework for circular gratings, we begin with the radial Helmholtz equation for an arbitrary azimuthal mode m

$$\frac{d^2 R}{d\rho^2} + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{dR}{d\rho} + \left(k_0^2 n^2(\rho) - \frac{m^2}{\rho^2} \right) R = 0$$

1.1 The Natural Coordinate

First we perform the standard substitution

$$R(\rho) = u(\rho)/\sqrt{\rho}$$

to eliminate the first derivative, yielding

$$\frac{d^2 u}{d\rho^2} + \left(k_0^2 n^2(\rho) - \frac{m^2 - 1/4}{\rho^2} \right) u = 0$$

We define the radial phase coordinate s exactly as the phase of Hankel function of the first kind ($H_m^1 = H_m$ with superscript omitted)

$$H_m(x) = M_m(x) e^{i\theta_m(x)}$$

Consequently, s serves as the "natural" space for periodicity, defined as

$$s \equiv \theta_m(k\rho)$$

Here, k is the real-space wave-vector defined as

$$k = k_0 n_{bg}$$

Where n_{bg} is the refractive index of the bulk material in which the grating is etched or deposited. This serves as the reference point for all perturbations.

Then we define the background wave-vector K_{bg} in s -space as Hankel phase derivative

$$K_{bg}(\rho) \equiv \frac{ds}{d\rho} = \frac{d\theta_m(k\rho)}{d\rho}$$

Utilize the Wronskian identity for the Hankel functions, expressed in modulus-phase form as

$$M_m^2(x) \frac{d\theta_m}{dx} = \frac{2}{\pi x}$$

The Hankel phase derivative becomes

$$K_{bg}(\rho) = \frac{2}{\pi\rho M_m^2(k\rho)}$$

By applying the Liouville transformation

$$u = \chi K_{bg}^{-1/2}$$

The physical field is given by

$$R(\rho) = \chi(s(\rho)) / \sqrt{\rho K_{bg}(\rho)}$$

And the equation for $\chi(s)$ becomes exactly

$$\frac{d^2\chi}{ds^2} + [1 + V(s)]\chi = 0$$

The effective potential $V(s)$ represents the "perturbation" of the grating relative to the cylindrical vacuum and consists of three parts, which are the background offset $B(s)$, grating potential $W(s)$ and curvature potential $Q(s)$. These are related by

$$V(s) = B(s) + W(s) + Q(s)$$

In the following sections, both potentials will be investigated in details. As will be shown, $B(s)$ and $Q(s)$ decay as $1/\rho^4$, and $B(s) + Q(s) = 0$, so we first examine $W(s)$.

1.2 The Grating Potential

The expression for $W(s)$ is given by

$$W(s) = \frac{k_0^2(n^2(\rho(s)) - n_{bg}^2)}{K_{bg}^2(\rho(s))}$$

Define the physical refractive index contrast as

$$\Delta n^2(\rho) = n^2(\rho) - n_{bg}^2$$

To make $V(s)$ perfectly periodic, and thus support a truly rigorous Bloch Wave, $W(s)$ needs to be perfectly periodic, such that

$$W(s) = W(s + L_s)$$

This necessitates the use of a conformal Grating. Specifically, to establish true periodicity in the s -domain, $W(s)$ must be explicitly satisfy two fundamental modulation requirements.

Placement modulation: The physical boundaries of the grating interfaces must map to uniformly spaced intervals in the natural coordinate s . This requires chirping the physical period in real space to maintain a constant period L_s in s -space. For circular gratings, the placement modulation is straightforward to implement during fabrication.

Contrast modulation: Because the background wave vector $K_{bg}^2(\rho)$ is in the denominator, the physical refractive index contrast cannot be constant. Since $K_{bg}^2(\rho)$ varies with ρ , one must vary the refractive index contrast $\Delta n^2(\rho)$ such that

$$\Delta n^2(\rho) \propto K_{bg}^2(\rho)$$

This compensates for the curvature of the space, ensuring the amplitude of the potential remains constant across periods.

Contrast modulation can be achieved through two primary approaches.

Graded material: Using techniques such as co-sputtering, it is possible to create a gradient in the material composition, thus in the refractive index.

Effective medium modulation: Instead of changing the material composition, one can change the duty cycle (the width-to-period ratio) of the gratings. By making the high-index part of the gratings slightly wider or narrower as a function of ρ , the effective Δn^2 to compensate for the $1/K_{bg}^2$ factor.

By designing the grating this way, one can create an effectively "straightened" s-space. The wave travelling through this radially chirped, index-modulated grating behaves exactly like a 1D plane wave propagating through a standard Bragg stack.

1.3 The Background Offset and the Curvature Potential

With the first term $W(s)$ now perfectly periodic, the only remaining non-periodic are $B(s)$ and $Q(s)$, but as will be discussed, they vanish quickly in the far field.

The background offset $B(s)$ is derived from the derivatives of the coordinate mapping

$$B(s) = \frac{k_0^2 n_{bg}^2 - (m^2 - 1/4)/\rho^2}{K_{bg}^2(\rho)} - 1$$

By substituting K_{bg} , it can be shown that $B(s)$ decays as $1/\rho^4$ for large radius. Because $B(s)$ decays faster than $1/s$, it is absolutely integrable on the interval $[s_0, \infty)$.

$$\int_{s_0}^{\infty} |B(s)| ds < \infty$$

The Curvature Potential $Q(s)$ is

$$Q(s) = \frac{3 (K_{bg}')^2}{4 K_{bg}^4} - \frac{1 K_{bg}''}{2 K_{bg}^3}$$

By substituting K_{bg} , it can be shown that $Q(s)$ decays as $1/\rho^4$ for large radius. Because $Q(s)$ decays faster than $1/s$, it is absolutely integrable on the interval $[s_0, \infty)$.

$$\int_{s_0}^{\infty} |Q(s)| ds < \infty$$

According to the Levinson's Theorem for linear differential equations, if the perturbation $B(s)$ and $Q(s)$ is absolutely integrable, the solutions to the perturbed equation asymptotically approach the exact solutions of the unperturbed periodic equation. It means both $B(s)$ and $Q(s)$ can be omitted when solving for $\chi(s)$ at large radius.

1.3.1 The Sum of Background Offset and Curvature Potential

When there is no grating, the grating potential $W(s) = 0$. There is only a uniform background dielectric with refractive index of n_{bg} . The solution to the cylindrical Helmholtz's equation will be Hankel functions. As demonstrated in the following sections, $R(\rho) = (\pi/2)^{1/2} M_m(k\rho) \chi(s)$, and $H_m = M_m e^{i\theta m}$, it follows that $\chi(s) \propto e^{is}$. Thus the function $\chi(s)$ is a solution to the equation

$$\frac{d^2\chi}{ds^2} + \chi = 0$$

Compare this equation to the equation for $\chi(s)$ above, it is evident that $V(s) = 0$. Then

$$B(s) + Q(s) = 0$$

Therefore, $B(s)$ and $Q(s)$ cancel each other out. And we have $V(s) = W(s)$. Even without resorting to the Levinson's Theorem, the following Bloch theorem for $\chi(s)$ can be applied.

2. Bloch Theorem in Natural Coordinate

Because the ideal conformal circular grating satisfies both placement and contrast modulation, the effective potential $V(s)$ becomes strictly periodic in the asymptotic approximation. Such that

$$V(s) = V(s + L_s)$$

Consequently the solution $\chi(s)$ to transformed Helmholtz equation takes the following form in the s -domain

$$\chi(s) = e^{iK_{\text{Bloch}}s} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} a_n e^{i \cdot n \cdot s \cdot G}$$

Here, the Bloch vector is limited to the first Brillouin zone.

$$K_{\text{Bloch}} \in [-\pi/L_s, \pi/L_s]$$

And

$$G = 2\pi/L_s$$

Thus the standard Bloch Theorem applies

$$\chi(s + L_s) = e^{iK_{\text{Bloch}}L_s}\chi(s)$$

Since s is phase and dimensionless, K_{Bloch} is a normalized dimensionless wave-vector suited for the "straightened" s -space. It is important to note that the radial Bloch theorem formally applies to the asymptotic case.

3. Mapping Back to Real Space

To map the solution from $\chi(s)$ to $R(\rho)$, recall that

$$K_{\text{bg}}(\rho) = \frac{ds}{d\rho} = k \frac{d\theta_m}{d(k\rho)} = \frac{2}{\pi\rho M_m^2(k\rho)}$$

Substituting the identity for ρK_{bg}

$$\rho K_{\text{bg}}(\rho) = \frac{2}{\pi M_m^2(k\rho)}$$

We obtain

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{\rho K_{\text{bg}}(\rho)}} = \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}} M_m(k\rho)$$

Thus, the exact mapping is

$$R(\rho) = \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}} M_m(k\rho) \chi(s)$$

This demonstrate that the physical field R is exactly a "Bloch function in s-space" modulated by the Hankel modulus

$$R(\rho) = M_m(k\rho) \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} a_n e^{i(K_{\text{Bloch}} + n \cdot G)s(\rho)}$$

Therefore, the Bloch condition in real space manifests as a radial automorphy condition

$$R(\rho(s + L_s)) = R(\rho(s)) e^{iK_{\text{Bloch}}L_s} \frac{M_m(k\rho(s + L_s))}{M_m(k\rho(s))}$$

The exact automorphy factor across one period is defined as

$$\gamma = \frac{M_m(k\rho(s + L_s))}{M_m(k\rho(s))} e^{iK_{\text{Bloch}}L_s}$$

Our goal is to express this using an effective medium Hankel wave formulation

$$\gamma_{\text{eff}} = \frac{H_m(\beta\rho(s + L_s))}{H_m(\beta\rho(s))}$$

Utilizing the modulus-phase definition of Hankel function, we expand γ_{eff} as

$$\gamma_{\text{eff}} = \frac{M_m(\beta\rho(s + L_s))}{M_m(\beta\rho(s))} e^{i[\theta_m(\beta\rho(s + L_s)) - \theta_m(\beta\rho(s))]}$$

To equate γ to γ_{eff} , two distinct conditions must be satisfied, i.e., the phase matching and modulus matching.

By equating the exponential terms, the total phase accumulated by the effective Hankel wave over one physical period (from ρ_1 to ρ_2) must exactly equal the Bloch phase advancement.

$$\theta_m(\beta\rho_2) - \theta_m(\beta\rho_1) = K_{\text{Bloch}}L_s$$

In differential form, the equation becomes

$$\frac{d\theta_m(\beta\rho)}{d\rho} = K_{\text{Bloch}}k$$

This guarantee phase equivalence across the period.

Utilizing the Wronskian identity, the exact spatial relationship between the modulus is

$$\frac{M_m^2(k\rho)}{M_m^2(\beta\rho)} = \frac{d\theta_m(\beta\rho)/d\rho}{d\theta_m(k\rho)/d\rho}$$

In the asymptotic approximation

$$d\theta_m(x)/dx \approx 1$$

Thus, the ratio of modulus square becomes

$$\frac{M_m^2(k\rho)}{M_m^2(\beta\rho)} = \frac{\beta}{k}$$

It becomes evident that by defining the effective medium wave vector as

$$\beta \equiv K_{\text{Bloch}}k$$

The modulus matching condition is inherently satisfied

$$\frac{M_m(\beta\rho_1)}{M_m(\beta\rho_2)} = \frac{M_m(k\rho_1)}{M_m(k\rho_2)}$$

The phase matching requirement is met as well.

Thus, the Bloch condition in the in the adiabatic limit is given by

$$R(\rho(s + L_s)) = R(\rho(s)) \frac{H_m(\beta\rho(s + L_s))}{H_m(\beta\rho(s))}$$

This represents the Bloch theorem for conformal grating (featuring both placement and contrast modulation) in real space.

Dividing both sides by Hankel function yields

$$\frac{R(\rho(s + L_s))}{H_m(\beta\rho(s + L_s))} = \frac{R(\rho(s))}{H_m(\beta\rho(s))}$$

Define the ratio as

$$P(s) = \frac{R(\rho(s))}{H_m(\beta\rho(s))}$$

It is evident that $P(s)$ is periodic with period L_s

$$P(s + L_s) = P(s)$$

Therefore, the general solution for the radial field is

$$R(\rho) = P(s(\rho))H_m(\beta\rho)$$

This is the exact cylindrical equivalent of a standard 1D Bloch wave, $\psi(x) = f(x)e^{ikx}$, where $f(x)$ is periodic.

4. Error Estimation for Hankel-Phase Gratings

A standard Hankel-phase grating defines its interfaces exactly according to the phase coordinate s . Therefore, it perfectly satisfies the placement modulation requirement. However, the refractive index contrast Δn^2 typically remains constant value, failing the contrast modulation requirement.

Recall that the grating potential $W(s)$

$$W(s) = \frac{k_0^2(n^2(\rho(s)) - n_{\text{bg}}^2)}{K_{\text{bg}}^2(\rho(s))}$$

In the asymptotic approximation

$$K_{\text{bg}}^2(\rho) \approx k_0^2 n_{\text{bg}}^2 - \frac{m^2 - 1/4}{\rho^2}$$

Using the asymptotic expansion for the Hankel phase derivative, we get Taylor expansion

$$W(s) \approx \frac{\Delta n^2}{n_{bg}^2} \left(1 + \frac{m^2 - 1/4}{(k_0 n_{bg} \rho)^2} \right) \approx U_0(s) + \delta V(s)$$

The ideal periodic square wave is

$$U_0(s) = \frac{\Delta n^2}{n_{bg}^2}$$

and the uncompensated perturbation or residual potential is

$$\delta V(s) = U_0(s) \frac{m^2 - 1/4}{(k_0 n_{bg} \rho)^2} = O\left(\frac{1}{s^2}\right)$$

Because standard fabrication utilizes a constant contrast, $W(s)$ is not perfectly periodic. The contrast error scales as $O(1/\rho^2)$.

4.1 Estimating the Bandgap Error

To derive the fractional error of the local Bragg frequency, we can use first-order perturbation theory on the local dispersion relation. In a periodic medium, the central Bragg frequency squared is inversely proportional to the effective local dielectric potential.

$$\omega_B^2 \propto 1 + V(s)$$

Thus the Bragg frequency ratio of Hankel-phased gratings to conformal gratings is

$$\left(\frac{\omega_B + \delta\omega_B}{\omega_B} \right)^2 = \frac{1 + U_0 + \delta V}{1 + U_0} = 1 + \frac{\delta V}{1 + U_0}$$

Taking the square root and applying $(1+x)^{1/2} \approx 1+x/2$ yields

$$\frac{\omega_B + \delta\omega_B}{\omega_B} \approx 1 + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\delta V}{1 + U_0}$$

The fractional error is then

$$\frac{\delta\omega_B}{\omega_B} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\delta V(s)}{1 + U_0(s)}$$

Thus, to leading order, the fractional error in the local Bragg frequency ω_B at radius ρ is

$$\frac{\delta\omega_B(\rho)}{\omega_B} \approx \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\Delta n^2/n_{bg}^2}{1 + \Delta n^2/n_{bg}^2} \right) \frac{m^2 - 1/4}{(k_0 n_{bg} \rho)^2}$$

4.2 Total Accumulated Phase Error

For a finite circular grating spanning from radius ρ_1 to ρ_2 , the breakdown of exact Bloch periodicity leads to a dephasing of the Bragg resonance. From the dispersion relation

$$K_B^2 = 1 + U_0$$

The first order variation gives

$$2K_B \delta K_B \approx \delta V$$

The accumulated phase error $\Delta\Phi_{\text{error}}$ across the grating is the integral of the wave vector shift.

$$\Delta\Phi_{\text{error}} = \int_{s(p_1)}^{s(p_2)} \delta K_B(s) ds \approx \int_{s_1}^{s_2} \frac{\delta V(s)}{2K_B(s)} ds$$

Substitute $\delta V(s)$ and using the $s \approx k_0 n_{\text{bg}} \rho$ yields

$$\Delta\Phi_{\text{error}} \approx \frac{U_0(m^2 - 1/4)}{2K_B k_0 n_{\text{bg}}} \left(\frac{1}{\rho_1} - \frac{1}{\rho_2} \right)$$

It demonstrates that the error is inversely proportional to the starting radius ρ_1 . If $\Delta\Phi_{\text{error}} \ll \pi$, the standard Hankel-phased grating behaves virtually identically to the ideal conformal grating, rendering the Radial Bloch Theorem a robust adiabatic approximation. However, for highly confined modes (large m) or gratings starting very close to the origin (small ρ_1), $\Delta\Phi_{\text{error}}$ approaches π . This causes destructive interference that severely degrades the quality factor (Q-factor) of the radial cavity. In such regimes, the conformal scaling of the index contrast becomes strictly necessary.

5. Discussion and Summary

This supplement establishes a rigorously exact generalized Bloch condition for cylindrical coordinates by defining the ideal conformal circular grating. We have proven that true radial periodicity requires both phase-matched boundary placement and conformal amplitude scaling of the refractive index contrast to counteract the curvature of the cylindrical metric.

Furthermore, we demonstrate that the formulations presented in previous direct calculations of radial band structures remain highly valid as an adiabatic approximation. Standard Hankel-phase gratings often omit contrast modulation, introducing a residual potential $\delta V(s)$. Because this error decays asymptotically, as long as the accumulated phase error $\Delta\Phi_{\text{error}}$ across the finite grating remains significantly less than π , the exact Bloch theorem derived here provides a robust and highly accurate mathematical foundation for evaluating standard circular gratings.